

Yield Uncertainty Assessments: CRD42023425955 Protocol Section (1)

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1 PRELIMINARY NOTE

Any quantitative research, especially in the industrial, health and safety areas, should add to efforts for the adequate expression of the uncertainties linked to the data of the experiments, care whose need is increasingly perceived (2–13). After the general metrological observations on the state of the art found, the procedures adopted and recommended care must be explained, as shown below.

2 ARTICLES AND REVIEWS

Data on the yield or yield of PC extraction methods, contained in articles and reviews, focus on measurement uncertainties expressed as standard deviations, sometimes called Type A standard uncertainties (14,15). In general, they elide assessments of Type B uncertainties, they do not assess combined or expanded uncertainties (and their coverage factor) and other metrological procedures necessary for certain industrial and commercial applications, as well as for adapting the quality of information to requirements in healthcare areas and security (15).

Considering that the practical restrictions of time and resources rarely allow a metrological treatment by statistical means (when all the magnitudes on which the result of a measurement depends are varied), the uncertainty is usually evaluated through mathematical models of the measurement and by the law of propagation of uncertainties (15,16). For this literature, therefore, Type A standard uncertainties u will be expressed, where available or calculable. In one case (17), the standard deviation (SD) for octacosanol and triacontanol contents was provided by the authors; thus,

$$u_r = \sqrt{SD_1^2 + SD_2^2 + \dots + SD_n^2} \quad (1)$$

where u is the Type A standard uncertainties and the subscript "r" indicates the technological route, the subscripts 1, 2, ... n indicate the specific standard deviations of component.

3 PATENTS

Practical impossibilities explain only part of the problems, which are not exhausted without considering that the culture of evaluating uncertainties has not been sufficiently disseminated in our time and that, on the other hand, there are incentives not to include in patents data that guarantee reproducibility of experiments with estimated uncertainties. In general, patents in this field of research do not assess uncertainties, although they often express intervals of yield with maximum (Max) and minimum (Min) values. When, as in the referred cases, it is only possible to estimate extremes, it can be provisionally

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assumed that the probability that the yield is within the referred extremes is equal to one and outside it is zero, characteristic of a uniform or rectangular symmetric distribution, therefore, adopted here for the preliminary estimation of standard uncertainty $u(x_i)$.

Formally, this function and probability density function (PDF) is conditioned as follows:

$$\zeta f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{a_+ - a_-}, & a_- \leq x \leq a_+ \\ 0, & a_- > x > a_+ \end{cases} \quad \text{and } P(x) = \int_{a_-}^{a_+} f(x) dx = \int_{a_-}^{a_+} \frac{1}{a_+ - a_-} dx = 1 \quad (2)$$

Where the extremes a_+ and a_- are, respectively, the limits of the right and left sides in relation to the midpoint 0 of the interval [Max, Min]. The expected value ($E[x]$) of the yield is

$$\mu_x = \int_{a_-}^{a_+} x f(x) dx = \frac{1}{a_+ - a_-} \cdot \left(\frac{x^2}{2} \right) \Big|_{a_-}^{a_+} = \frac{a_+ + a_-}{2} \quad (3)$$

Remembering that

$$E[x^2] = \int_{a_-}^{a_+} x^2 f(x) dx = \frac{1}{a_+ - a_-} \cdot \left(\frac{x^3}{3} \right) \Big|_{a_-}^{a_+} = \frac{a_+^3 - a_-^3}{3(a_+ - a_-)} \quad (4)$$

Then

$$u(x_i) = \sqrt{E[x^2] - \{E[x]\}^2} = \sqrt{\frac{a_+^3 - a_-^3}{3(a_+ - a_-)} - \left(\frac{a_+ + a_-}{2} \right)^2} = \sqrt{\frac{(a_+ - a_-)^2}{12}} \quad (5)$$

If $(a_+ - a_-)$ is designated by $2a$, becomes $u(x_i) = \frac{a}{\sqrt{3}}$ (15).

Considering that the standard uncertainty $u(x_i)$ will be evaluated based on the applicants' experimental data on the variability of yield, it is used to call standard uncertainty Type B. This is valid until it is possible to obtain additional data, especially desirable when the procedure greatly affects the uncertainty about the yield. (15). Compared to the Type A uncertainty estimates given in the articles and reviews, these Type B estimates of patent $u(x_i)$ may not be as reliable, especially when based on a smaller number of statistically independent observations. In some cases, data from articles and reviews can require analogous treatment.

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